

TRANSPORT NUMBER OF LEAD AND CADMIUM IN THEIR NITRATES BY ANALYTICAL BOUNDARY METHOD.

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The transport number of cadmium and of lead in their nitrate solutions have been determined by analytical boundary method over the concentration range of 0.01M - 0.5M. In case of cadmium, with changes in concentration, the transport number decreases slowly (from 0.426 to 0.403) and in case of lead it shows an increase (0.40 to 0.49). The experimental results have been explained quantitatively in the light of interionic attraction and the incomplete dissociation of the intermediate ions.

In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 217) the transport number of cadmium in cadmium nitrate solution was determined by Hittorf's method. In the present investigation transport measurements have been made by analytical boundary method developed by Brady (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 911). Spiro and Patron (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, 48, 263) improved the experimental technique and determined the transport number of silver in silver nitrate at various concentrations using KNO_3 and NaNO_3 solutions as indicator solutions. Their results were correct to 7 in the fourth decimal place. This accuracy compares fairly well with those ordinarily obtained from moving boundary experiments and cannot be achieved by Hittorf's method.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus was more or less the same as that used by Spiro and Patron (*loc. cit.*). They used an electronically controlled constant current source and checked the constancy of the current by means of a potentiometer. In this work, however, voltage was kept constant by means of a voltage regulator and the total electricity passed was measured by a silver coulometer, and in some cases by silver as well as iodine coulometers. The working of the apparatus was tested from time to time by determining the transport number of silver ion in silver nitrate solution.

Merck's analytical reagent lead nitrate and cadmium nitrate were used. Ferric nitrate was prepared by dissolving precipitated and washed $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ in extra pure nitric acid. Extra pure lead and cadmium were used as anode.

Cadmium was determined either iodimetrically or sometimes gravimetrically with 8-hydroxyquinoline. Lead was estimated gravimetrically as lead chromate.

The concentration of the indicator solution was calculated by using Kohlrausch's relation. Transport number determinations were made with various concentrations of the indicator solutions, some higher and some lower than the Kohlrausch's concentration, and the transport values were found to be on the plateau region. Experiments were done in triplicate and the average values of the transport numbers and the deviations from the mean are indicated in Tables I and II.

The transport number of cadmium or lead has been calculated as the amount of the particular ion crossing the boundary in g. equiv./g. equiv. of silver deposited in the coulometer. The transport numbers, thus calculated, are shown in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Cd in cadmium nitrate soln.

Conc.	Transport number.
0.01 M	0.426 ± 0.002
0.02	0.416 ± 0.003
0.05	0.413 ± 0.003
0.10	0.413 ± 0.003
0.20	0.406 ± 0.002
0.50	0.403 ± 0.003

TABLE II

Pb in lead nitrate soln.

Conc.	Transport number.
0.015 M	0.46 ± 0.01
0.02	0.46 ± 0.003
0.05	0.47 ± 0.007
0.10	0.48 ± 0.004
0.25	0.49 ± 0.01
0.50	0.49 ± 0.01

DISCUSSION

From the results it appears that the transport number of cadmium in cadmium nitrate solution decreases with concentration (Table I) whereas in the case of lead in nitrate (Table II), the transport number increases with concentration. It may give the impression that there might be some defect in the experimental technique. Analysis of the data according to the scheme, discussed in the subsequent section, shows that it is not so. This apparent anomaly is due to the difference in the association constants of the intermediate ion (MA^+) in the two cases.

According to the usual definition, the transport number of anion in an electrolyte solution is the fraction of the total current passed, carried by that ion. This rather is a too much simplified definition of the transport number. This can be determined only when an electrolyte is completely dissociated in solution (nomenclature and definition: McBain, "Colloid Science", pp. 253-55; Alberty, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2361; Spiro, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1956, **33**, 464). When an electrolyte is not completely dissociated, then what we measure (by the ratio amount of a particular ion crossing the boundary in g. equiv./g. equiv. of silver deposited in the coulometer) is the transport number of the ion constituent (Spiro, *loc. cit.*) which is defined by the equation

$$T_R = \left(\frac{z_R}{z_R} \right) = \frac{\sum U_i m_i n_{R,i} \left(\frac{z_i}{|z_i|} \right)}{\sum U_i m_i |z_i|}$$

where T_R = transport number of the ion constituent R.

U_i = mobility of the species i .

m_i = molarity of the species i .

$n_{R,i}$ = number of g. equiv. of ion constituent R, in one g. formula wt. of species i .

z_i = algebraic equivalence per formula of the species i .

$$|z_i| = + \sqrt{z_i^2}$$

$\frac{z_R}{|z_R|} = + 1$ for cation species and $- 1$ for anion species.

Lead nitrate and cadmium nitrate may not exist in solution in completely dissociated state. Assuming the first stage of dissociation to be complete, the second incomplete and using the symbol MA_2 for $Pb(NO_3)_2$ or $Cd(NO_3)_2$, the equilibrium may be represented as

The transport number of the ion constituent M^{2+} ($T_{M^{2+}}^{MA_2}$) is given by,

$$T_{M^{2+}}^{MA_2} = \frac{2\alpha m U_{M^{2+}} + 2(1-\alpha)m U_{MA^+}}{2\alpha m U_{M^{2+}} + (1-\alpha)m U_{MA^+} + (1+\alpha)m U_{A^-}}$$

where α is the degree of dissociation of MA^+ and m , the molarity of the solution with respect to MA_2 .

To test this equation, one may calculate the $T_{M^{2+}}^{MA_2}$ from the equation and compare with the experimental values or using the experimental values calculate the dissociation constant and compare that with the value of the dissociation constant determined by other methods. This is difficult as U_{MA^+} cannot be determined directly.

The dissociation constants for $PbNO_3^+$, $CdNO_3^+$ have been reported from conductance measurements by Davies *et al.* (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 572). The value of the dissociation constant for $PbNO_3^+$ has also been recently obtained by Hershenson, Smith and Hume (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 507) and Bale, Davies and Monk (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 816) from spectrophotometric measurements. From these measurements one can get the value of α and take the value of U_{MA^+} either on the basis of Davies's assumption or nearly half that of $U_{Cd^{2+}}$ on an analogy between that of Cd^{2+} and CdI^+ (Alberty, *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 517).

If $T_{M^{2+}}^{MA_2}$ is calculated on this basis, it is found that the transport number should increase with concentration. For example, in case of cadmium nitrate, transport number will be 0.4306 when $\alpha=1$ and about 0.55 when $\alpha=0$ (*i.e.* when the species in the solution are $CdNO_3^+$ and NO_3^-). Similar will be the case with lead nitrate.

If no intermediate ions were formed, the transport number would have decreased with concentration due to the interionic attraction as in the case of $Zn(ClO_4)_2$ (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 338) and barium chloride.

So in case of electrolytes of the type MA_2 , where there are MA^+ ions, there will be two opposing factors affecting the value of the transport number: (i) interionic force which will tend to decrease the transport number with concentration, and (ii) partially dissociated intermediate ion which will lead to an increase in the value of the transport number with increase in concentration.

Therefore, depending on the magnitude of K (the dissociation constant) one or the other effect will be predominant or may balance. If K is large, the interionic effect

will be more, and there will be a decrease in the value of transport number with concentration. If K is such that the effect are comparable, then the transport number may decrease or increase with concentration depending on whichever factor is more effective. As pointed out earlier, only a semiquantitative analysis of the results is possible. It has also been mentioned earlier that since K for PbNO_3^+ is smaller than that for CdNO_3^+ , there would be more PbNO_3^+ than CdNO_3^+ in respective solutions at the same concentration. So increase with reference to the standard, say transport number for $\text{Zn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (assuming normal behaviour), the increase in $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ will be more than that in $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. That is what we find in analysing our results. These results thus may be taken to be indicating the presence of intermediate MA^+ ions. No attempts to calculate their equilibrium constant has been made as the accuracy is not high and uncertainty also lies about the mobility of MA^+ .

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